

SHERLOCK

Supporting the energy transition of the building stock

D2.3 Building energy renovation roadmap

June 2024

Pablo Baigorria Kobylinski (CREARA)
John Dennis Javien (CREARA)

D2.3 Building energy renovation roadmap	
Work Package	WP2 SHERLOCK's Pan-European Knowledge Centre creation
Task	Building energy renovation roadmap
Deliverable lead	CREARA
Author(s)	Pablo Baigorria Kobylinski (Creara) John Dennis Javien (Creara)
Grant Agreement number	101105629
Start date of the project / Duration	1 September 2023 / 36 months
Type of deliverable (R, DEM, DEC, other)	R
Dissemination level (PU, SEN)	PU
Date of first submission	29/06/2024
Final submission date	29/06/2024
Revision n°	1.0
Revision date	28/06/2024

R=Document, report; **DEM**=Demonstrator, pilot, prototype; **DEC**=website, patent fillings, videos, etc.; **OTHER**=other
PU = Public; **SEN** = Sensitive

Project overview

SHERLOCK aims to contribute to the EU's decarbonisation targets by co-designing a MOOC-based micro-master programme and a VET-oriented short training course with stakeholders, based on micro credentials and case study education, targeting students and professionals from both the building energy retrofitting and financial sectors. The project will help overcome the skills mismatch between financial operators and project developers to foster the acceleration of building energy retrofitting across Europe.

SHERLOCK is a 36-month project co-funded by the Erasmus+ Programme of the European Union under Grant Agreement 101105629. Coordinated by the University of Genoa (Italy), it gathers 17 partners from France, Greece, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Portugal, Slovakia, and Spain.

Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No 101105629. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Education and Culture Executive Agency (EACEA). Neither the European Union nor EACEA can be held responsible for them.

Table of contents

1	Executive Summary	10
2	Introduction.....	11
3	Overview of the EU building stock.....	11
3.1	Spain	12
3.1.1	National context	12
3.1.2	Quantification of the building stock	13
3.1.3	National Building Efforts	15
3.1.4	Prospects	17
3.2	Portugal	18
3.2.1	National context	18
3.2.2	Quantification of the building stock	19
3.2.3	National Building Efforts	20
3.2.4	Prospects	22
3.3	Italy	23
3.3.1	National context	23
3.3.2	Quantification of the building stock	23
3.3.3	National Building Efforts	25
3.3.4	Prospects	26
3.4	Ireland	27
3.4.1	National context	27
3.4.2	Quantification of the building stock	28
3.4.3	National Building Efforts	29
3.4.4	Prospects	30
3.5	Greece.....	32
3.5.1	National context	32
3.5.2	Quantification of the building stock	33
3.5.3	National Building Efforts	34
3.5.4	Prospects	35
3.6	Lithuania	36
3.6.1	National context	36
3.6.2	Quantification of the building stock	37
3.6.3	National Building Efforts	38
3.6.4	Prospects	40
3.7	Slovakia.....	41
3.7.1	National context	41

3.7.2	Quantification of the building stock	42
3.7.3	National Building Efforts	43
3.7.4	Prospects	44
4	Regulatory framework for Energy Efficiency in the European Union	46
4.1	Energy Performance of Buildings Directive	46
4.2	Energy Efficiency Directive	48
4.3	Fit for 55 Package	49
4.4	The Renovation Wave	50
4.5	National regulations in each country	50
4.6	Spain	50
4.7	Portugal	51
4.8	Italy	52
4.9	Ireland	52
4.10	Greece	53
4.11	Lithuania	53
4.12	Slovakia	54
5	FINANCIAL SCHEMES.....	55
5.1	Traditional financial instruments	55
5.1.1	Loans	55
5.1.2	Grants.....	56
5.1.3	Tax incentives.....	57
5.2	Innovative financial instruments	58
5.2.1	On-bill and on-tax schemes	58
5.2.2	Energy performance contracting (EPC)	59
5.2.3	Green debt	60
6	Barriers.....	61
6.1	Economic and financial barriers	61
6.2	Behavioural barriers	62
6.3	Information barriers	62
6.4	Administrative barriers.....	62
6.5	Technical barriers	62
6.6	Organisational barriers	63

7	Conclusions	63
8	References	65

List of figures

Figure 1 - Spanish building stock in a nutshell	13
Figure 2 – Climatic zones in Spain	15
Figure 3 - Spain's total investment in energy related renovations in (2016)	15
Figure 4 - Spain's renovation rate (2016)	17
Figure 5 - Portugal building stock in a nutshell.....	19
Figure 6 - Portugal's total investment in energy related renovations (2016)	20
Figure 7 - Portugal's renovation rate (2016)	22
Figure 8 - Italy building stock in a nutshell	24
Figure 9 - Italy’ s total investment in energy related renovations (2016)	25
Figure 10 – Italy’ s renovation rate (2016)	26
Figure 11 - Ireland building stock in a nutshell	28
Figure 12 - Ireland’ s total investment in energy related renovations (2016)	29
Figure 13 - Irelands’ renovation rate (2016)	30
Figure 14 - Greece building stock in a nutshell.....	33
Figure 15 - Greece’ s total investment in energy related renovations (2016)	34
Figure 16 - Greece’ s renovation rate (2016)	35
Figure 17 - Lithuania building stock in a nutshell.....	37
Figure 18 - Lithuania’ s total investments in energy related renovations (2016)	38
Figure 19 - Lithuania’ s renovation rate (2016)	39
Figure 20 - Slovakia building stock in a nutshell	42
Figure 21 - Slovakia’ s total investment in energy related renovations (2016)	43
Figure 22 - Slovakia’ s renovation rate (2016).....	44
Figure 23 - Requirements and deadlines, linked to NBRP and NECP cycles until 2034	48
Figure 24 - Most common innovative financing schemes	58

List of tables

Table 1 – Glossary9

Acronym	Meaning
CTE	Technical Building Code
EBRD	European Bank for Reconstruction and Development
EE	Energy Efficiency
EED	Energy Efficiency Directive
EPB	Energy Performance of Buildings
EPBD	Energy Performance of Building Directive
EPC	Engineering Procurement and Construction
ERESEE	Spanish Long-term Strategy for Energy Renovation in the Building Sector
ESCO	Energy Service Companies
ESIF	European Structural and Investment Funds
ETS	Emissions Trading System
GIB	Green Investment Bank
KENAK	Green Building Regulation
MEPS	The Minimum Energy Performance Standards
NBRP	National Building Renovation Plan
NECP	National Energy and Climate Plan
NEZB	Nearly Zero Energy Building
PAREER	Programme for financing the energy retrofit
PEC	Primary Energy Consumption
RCCTE	Thermal Performance Buildings Characteristics Regulation
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SCE	Energy Certification System
SEAI	Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland
SRI	Smart Readiness Indicator
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics

Table 1 – Glossary

1 Executive Summary

This report provides a detailed analysis of the current state and future challenges of building stocks in Spain, Italy, Portugal, Ireland, Greece, Lithuania and Slovakia, focusing on energy performance improvements. It identifies major barriers based on different data from EUROSTAT and the European Commission. Furthermore, the regulatory landscape is explored, highlighting EU directives like the EPBD, EED, Fit for 55 and the Renovation Wave, along with specific national strategies.

All regulations are crucial but also pose integration challenges across said countries. A significant gap identified is the investment needed to meet renovation targets. The report discusses both traditional and innovative financing schemes, emphasizing the need for private investment to supplement public funds. These schemes can increase renovation rates across EU member states.

To ensure effective investments, the report stresses the importance of equipping energy-efficient solution providers with adequate technical skills. Long-term, effective solutions depend on a well-trained labour force capable of designing and implementing energy saving measures.

The focus on consumer engagement is critical, as both households and businesses may lack awareness or economic incentive to assure energy renovations. Energy efficiency professionals must address social, technical and economic barriers comprehensively to overcome these barriers.

In conclusion, during the report it is reflected that to achieve the EU's energy performance objectives for building, substantial investment, enhanced skills, innovative financing and effective consumer engagement are needed.

2 Introduction

This report provides an overview of the building stock in the seven European countries participating in the SHERLOCK project. The aim of this document is to understand the challenges ahead, including the targets related to the energy performance of buildings and the main barriers to achieving them:

- **Chapter 2** presents the situation of the building stock in each of the countries studied (Spain, Italy, Portugal, Ireland, Greece, Lithuania and Slovakia). By reviewing both the current situation and the prospects, it is possible to identify the main barriers to energy renovation of buildings, namely the lack of necessary investment and the lack of skilled labor. The data used in this section are based on EUROSTAT and other databases provided by the European Commission, such as the Building Stock Observatory, and by each country analysed, such as the National Long-Term Renovation Strategies.
- **Chapter 3** presents the main regulatory frameworks in the European Union, focusing on the EPBD, the EED, Fit for 55 and the Renovation Wave, but also the main regulations and programmes introduced in each country analysed. This section is based on the literature review of the main European regulations mentioned, as well as on the National Long-Term Renovation Strategies.
- **Chapter 4** addresses the investment gap identified in Chapter 2 and explains the difference between traditional and innovative financing schemes. This section is based on the opinion of market experts gathered through a series of interviews conducted by CREARA and research papers dealing with this topic.
- **Chapter 5** outlines the barriers that may hinder efforts to achieve the European building renovation targets. It expands on and adds some of the barriers identified during the analysis process of the previous chapters. The identification of barriers was based both on the opinions of market experts and on the conclusions of the European Commission working documents.

3 Overview of the EU building stock

The green energy transition has become one of the most important items on the European agenda. The Member States are each year increasing the relevance of the renewable energy in their energy mix and there are far-reaching plans to achieve a cost-effective decarbonisation of the European energy system.

However, it is important to note that the least polluting energy source is energy that is not consumed. The new regulations targeting net zero energy buildings only apply to new buildings. Oppositely, the EU building stock is old, meaning that there are buildings that would not comply with the updated minimum criteria. More than 40% of the European building stock was built before 1960 and 90% before 1990, when there were virtually no energy efficiency regulations in place. Nearly 75% of the EU building stock is considered energy inefficient and in need of renovation. As a result, nearly 40% of the total final energy consumption and 36% of greenhouse emissions in the EU are linked to the EU building stock [1].

Although the European Commission has taken several measures to incentivise energy renovation of buildings, most renovations do not result in significant reductions in energy consumption and are labelled as “below threshold” (less than 3% energy savings). This is due to several factors:

- From an economic point of view, these types of renovations entail lower costs than deeper renovations, as they provide a faster return on investment.
- From an infrastructural point of view, this type of renovation can be completed with minimal disruption, unlike deep renovations that usually cause inconvenience.

Each country has some specific conditions that influence the level of renovation. It is therefore necessary to understand the national context before making recommendations on how to address the issue of energy renovation of buildings.

3.1 Spain

3.1.1 National context

In Spain, the building stock is diverse and characterized by a significant number of buildings (61%) built before 1990, including residential, commercial, industrial, and public buildings. The first reform of the Technical Building Code (CTE) that included energy efficiency criteria was approved in 1998 [2]. The presence of older buildings throughout the country highlights the need for efficiency improvements and energy consumption reduction, as many of these buildings were built before such criteria.

Spain’s legislative framework plays a crucial role in guiding the renovation of the building stock. The Minimum Energy Performance Standards (MEPS) established in the Technical Building Code (CTE) are mandatory for newly constructed buildings and those undergoing renovations involving 25% or more of the building envelope, and they are restrictive enough to ensure that a

building has an energy performance rating of A (NZEB level) [3]. Energy efficiency requirements have progressively increased over time, the first ones appeared in 1998 marking the beginning of a legislative focus on energy efficiency. Since then, these regulations have been adapted, reflecting advancements in technology and increasing awareness of environmental issues. The CTE is frequently revised and with each new publication, the energy efficiency requirements become more stringent.

As a result, the minimum requirements established by the CTE are of particular importance, they ensure that buildings undergoing significant renovations will have to meet these standards, which will significantly enhance their energy efficiency.

3.1.2 Quantification of the building stock

Figure 1 - Spanish building stock in a nutshell [4]

Spain’s building stock totals approximately 10,300,000 buildings, including both residential and non-residential buildings. Of these, 8,817,432 are residential, representing about 86% of the total, and 1,481,117 are non-residential, accounting for the remaining 14% [4].

In the residential sector, there are 2,778,508 apartment buildings and 6,038,924 single-family houses. Despite the larger number of single-family houses, it is the apartment blocks that accommodate about 66% of the population, which is indicative of a preference in Spain apartment buildings [5]. Single-family houses, which are easier to renovate due to fewer obstacles, allow for straightforward

implementation of energy efficiency upgrades. In contrast, apartment blocks, while more complex due to the need for coordination among multiple owners, offer a higher cumulative impact on energy savings when renovated [5]. In Spain, apartment buildings are managed by homeowners' associations, where all owners must agree to invest in renovations. This process can be challenging due to the need for consensus among numerous residents. However, investing in the renovation of apartment buildings is crucial for achieving substantial energy savings on a larger scale.

The breakdown of non-residential buildings shows the diversity of activities supported by the non-residential infrastructure, including 35,390 educational facilities, 27,860 health facilities, 147,584 hotels and restaurants, 150,596 offices, 971,348 wholesale and retail buildings, and 148,337 buildings serving other purposes, such as buildings used for religious, cultural, recreational and public service activities [4]. This diversity in the non-residential sector calls for sector specific strategies in energy management and infrastructure development as each type has unique energy needs and usage patterns.

Ownership is the predominant tenure status within the residential market, with 76% of dwellings owned by the residents, while 24% are rented [7]. This high rate of ownership reduces the importance of the "split incentives" problem in Spain. "Split Incentives" is a barrier to energy renovation that depicts the low incentives a homeowner must renovate a rental property. This is due to the fact that the owner does not have any direct economic benefit (the energy bills are payable by the tenant) nor has an increase in comfort.

Energy consumption details are also significant, with the final household consumption totalling 609,522 TJ. Of this, space heating accounts for about 40%, illustrating its dominance in energy use. Lighting and electrical appliances after space heating accounts for 31%. Water heating makes up approximately 19%, cooking accounts for roughly 8%, space cooling for 1%, and other end use appliances also consume about 1% [8]. The high percentage of space heating is due the fact that Spain's climate varies significantly from the cooler northern regions to the warmer southern and coastal areas. In the northern regions, winter temperatures can be quite low, necessitating substantial energy use for heating. The CTE defines different climatic zones for the country, considering temperature and climate assumptions used in the calculation of energy performance certificates. For example, in the northern areas and high-altitude zones, the demand for heating is much higher compared to the southern and coastal areas, where cooling might be more prevalent. **Error! Reference source not found.** shows a summary of the CTE climatic zones in Spain:

Parameters	Description	Provinces
Zone A	Warm coastal areas with mild winters and hot summers	Cádiz, Málaga, Ceuta, Melilla, Las Palmas, Santa Cruz de Tenerife
Zone B	Inland areas with cold winters and hot summers	Huelva, Sevilla, Córdoba, Murcia, Alicante, Valencia, Castellón, Tarragona, Islas Baleares
Zone C	Northern coastal areas with mild winters and summers	Coruña, Pontevedra, Orense, Asturias, Cantabria, Vizcaya, Guipúzcoa, Barcelona, Gerona, Cáceres, Badajoz, Toledo, Jaén, Granada
Zone D	High-altitude areas with cold winters and mild summers	Lugo, Zamora, Salamanca, Valladolid, Palencia, Segovia, Madrid, Guadalajara, Cuenca, Albacete, Ciudad Real, Teruel, Zaragoza, La Rioja, Álava, Navarra, Huesca, Lérida
Zone E	Mountainous regions with very cold winters and cool summers	León, Burgos, Soria, Ávila

Figure 2 – Climatic zones in Spain [3]

3.1.3 National Building Efforts

Total investment in energy related renovations

Figure 3 - Spain's total investment in energy related renovations in (2016) [9]

The analysis of building renovation investments has been structured around the depth of renovations, categorised according to their energy saving potential [9]. The distribution of these investments across residential and non-residential buildings is as follows:

- **Below threshold renovations**, which achieve less than 3% energy savings, see the most substantial investments with residential properties receiving 10,527 million Euros, significantly more than the 1,247 million Euros allocated to non-residential properties. This indicates a focus on performing basic maintenance and minor aesthetic upgrades primarily within the residential sector. Examples of these renovations include changing windows, repainting, minor roof repairs or installing new flooring materials for example.
- **Light renovations**, which result in energy savings between 3% and 30%, investment is well-distributed across building types. Residential renovations in this category attract 1,875 million Euros, slightly higher than the 1,725 million Euros directed towards non-residential buildings. This suggests a common approach to moderate upgrades that enhance energy efficiency without extensive structural changes. Examples of light renovations include installing more efficient heating systems, adding insulation to walls and roofs, for example.
- **Medium renovations**, offering energy savings between 30% and 60%, show an opposite trend in funding priority. In this case, non-residential buildings receive a higher investment of 2,649 million Euros compared to 1,154 million Euros for residential buildings. This indicates a stronger emphasis on significant improvements in the commercial and industrial sectors, most likely due to the greater impact and return on investment that these savings can provide for their operations. Examples of medium renovations include comprehensive insulation upgrades, like installation of advanced heating, ventilations and air conditioning systems for example.
- **Deep renovations**, which achieve energy savings of more than 60%, are the least invested category and show a clear preference for non-residential buildings. These deep renovations are crucial to bring older buildings up to modern energy standards and typically involve structural upgrades. Examples of deep renovations include complete building envelope, installation of renewable energy systems, smart building integration and many other renovations.

Influenced by the degree of investment, the renovation rate varies accordingly. In its current form, it is not big enough to achieve the necessary goals. Figure 4 shows the national renovation rate by type of renovation and type of building.

Figure 4 - Spain's renovation rate (2016) [9]

3.1.4 Prospects

The prospect for the renovation of Spain’s building stock aims to outline the vision for the decarbonisation by 2050. It details the projected evolution of energy consumption, energy saving targets and required investments.

In 2020, the residential sector in Spain consumed 172,419 GWh of final energy, while the tertiary sector consumed 131,858 GWh. The emissions from these sectors amounted to 14,799,503 tCO₂. These numbers serve as the baseline for setting the future targets and evaluating progress [9].

By 2030, significant steps will be taken to reduce energy consumption and emissions. Residential energy consumption is expected to decrease to 146,025 GWh, accompanied by energy savings of 26,394 GWh. On the other hand, the tertiary sector is expected to maintain its energy consumption at 2020 levels. The renovation of 1.2 million dwellings is planned, for which public and private investment totalling 41,471 million Euros will be required, of which 15,520 million Euros will be private investment for replacing obsolete ACS/heating equipment, and 6,946 million Euros public investment to support the rehabilitation and replacement of equipment [10].

The ultimate goals for 2050 focus on substantial reduction in energy consumption and emissions where residential energy consumption will be lowered to 108,264 GWh, representing a 37% reduction compared to 2020

levels, and the tertiary sector will see a reduction in energy consumption to 84,463 GWh, achieving a 36% decrease compared to 2020. Residential buildings will achieve a 99% reduction in CO₂ emissions, with heating consumption reduced to less than 55% of 2020 levels. Furthermore, a total of 7.1 million homes are expected to undergo deep renovation, lowering individual consumption to 12 kWh/m². The construction of 3.9 million new homes, all meeting NZEB standards, is also planned [10].

Spain's building stock faces a transformative future with ambitious plans for energy efficiency, driven by nation and EU policies. To reach the objectives, government support and financial incentives are necessary. Several programmes, such as the PAREER II programme for financing the energy retrofit, which provides financial aid and low interest loans for actions that reach energy class A and B or that increase the initial energy rating of the existing building by more than two letters lead to significant improvements in energy efficiency.

It is expected, that by 2050, the residential sector alone will require 143 billion Euros in investments [10].

The vision for the decarbonisation of Spain's building stock by 2050 is ambitious, significant investments, coordinated efforts and comprehensive policy measures are needed. The outline targets and milestones of the national long term renovation strategies provide a clear roadmap.

3.2 Portugal

3.2.1 National context

There are about 3 million residential buildings in Portugal, being this nearly 3 times more than non-residential buildings. The Portuguese residential building stock is notably aged, with 15% of the buildings dating back to 1945 or earlier. About 70% were built prior to 1990, when energy performance regulations for residential buildings were still not implemented in the country.

The first Portuguese regulation on the energy performance of buildings (EPB) was implemented in 1990, designed for new buildings and major renovation. Subsequently, it was replaced by the Thermal Performance Buildings Characteristics Regulation (RCCTE) in 2006 and the Energy Certification System (SCE). Over the years, these regulations were amended, and Portugal has adapted to the EU legislation [11]

As other EU countries, it is relevant to point out that some of the older buildings have a historical and architectural value that, according to the regulation, must

be preserved, constituting a constraint on the implementation of various thermal improvement measures.

Although Portuguese homes are not energy efficient, they also have some of the lowest energy consumption rates in the EU [8].

Improving the energy efficiency of the housing stock is a priority for the Portuguese government for decreasing energy poverty in the country. The government has approved the Long-term Plan for the Renovation of Buildings, which highlights the need for considerable investment. Under the national action plan for energy efficiency, a programme called “Aviso 25” was launched to finance up to 60% of energy efficiency measures for residential and service buildings [11].

3.2.2 Quantification of the building stock

Figure 5 - Portugal building stock in a nutshell [4]

Portugal’s building stock totals approximately 3,617,308 buildings, which includes both residential and non-residential buildings. Of these, 2,898,333 are residential, constituting about 80% of the total, while 718,975 are classified as non-residential, accounting for the remaining 20% [4].

In the residential sector, there are 395,495 apartment blocks and 2,502,837 single-family houses. We can see a variety of housing preferences in Portugal, with single-family homes being the more popular choice overall (83%) [5].

The breakdown of non-residential buildings shows the diversity of activities supported by the non-residential infrastructure, including 22,431 educational facilities, 18,889 health facilities, 30,695 hotels and restaurants, 94,446 offices, 526,540 wholesale and retail buildings, and 25,972 buildings serving other purposes [4].

Ownership is more common than renting in the residential market, with 78% of homes owned by residents, while only 22% are rented [7].

Energy consumption data show that the final consumption of household in Portugal amounts to 126,508 TJ. Of these, space heating is the largest segment, with 31%, demonstrating its dominance in energy use. This is followed by food cooking which accounts for nearly 31%, lighting and electrical appliances 20%, water heating 17% and space cooling 1% [8].

3.2.3 National Building Efforts

Figure 6 - Portugal's total investment in energy related renovations (2016) [13]

The analysis of investments in building renovations has been organized based on the extent of renovations, categorised by their potential for energy savings [13]. The allocations of these investments between residential and non-residential buildings are detailed as follows:

- **Below threshold renovations** receive the largest share of investments, with residential properties receiving 1.135 million Euros, substantially more than the 232 million Euros allocated to non-residential properties. This suggests a primary focus on basic maintenance and minor aesthetic improvements in the residential sector.
- **Light renovations** investments are more evenly distributed across building types. Residential properties receive 1,014 million Euros, which is significantly higher than the 274 million Euros allocated to non-residential buildings. This indicates a widespread approach to moderate upgrades that improves energy efficiency without extensive structural modifications.
- **Medium renovations** display a different funding trend. In this category, non-residential buildings receive more investment, with 424 million Euros compared to 288 million Euros for residential buildings. This highlights a greater focus on substantial improvements in the commercial and industrial sectors, probably due to the greater impact and return on investment of these energy savings.
- **Deep renovations**, receive the least investment and show a clear preference for non-residential buildings. These extensive renovations are essential for updating older buildings to modern energy standards and typically involve significant structural upgrades.

Influenced by the degree of investment, the renovation rate varies accordingly. Figure 7 shows the national renovation rate by type of renovation and type of building.

Figure 7 - Portugal's renovation rate (2016) [13]

3.2.4 Prospects

The prospects for the renovation of Portugal’s Building Stock aims to provide a detailed roadmap that highlights the steps necessary to achieve a sustainable and energy-efficient building sector.

Regarding renovation milestones by 2050, Portugal aims to renovate 747,953,071 m² of its building stock. Intermediate targets include 363,680,051 m² by 2030 and 635,637,685 m² by 2040. This extensive renovation effort should significantly reduce primary energy consumption [11]

Energy efficiency improvements are key to Portugal’s decarbonisation strategy. Primary energy savings are projected to reach 11% by 2030, increasing to 27% in 2040 and 34% in 2050. These savings are key to reduce the environmental impact of buildings and achieving near Zero Energy Building (NZEB) efficiency by 2050. Specifically, a cumulative primary energy savings of 40%, is expected for residential buildings, while for non-residential buildings a reduction of 28% reduction is expected, leading to a total cutback of 34% by 2050. Among these, the reduction of CO₂ emissions is a key objective, with targets set for a 45-55% emission reduction by 2030 [11].

The renovation strategy includes specific targets for both public and private buildings. For the non-residential sector, which includes education, health,

sports facilities and public administration services, the renovation targets are set to reach 50% by 2030, 75% by 2040 and 100% by 2050. This translates to an annual renovation rate of 5% in the first decade and 2.5% in the following decades. For private buildings the targets are similar: 25% of the building stock by 2030, 50% by 2040, and between 75% and 100% by 2050 [11].

To achieve these ambitious goals, substantial financial investment will be required. The estimated total investment needed by 2050 is 143,492 million Euros, of which 113,579 million Euros are allocated to the residential sector and 33,414 million Euros to the non-residential sector [11]. This level of investment highlights the level of commitment required from both public and private sectors to achieve the set goals.

3.3 Italy

3.3.1 National context

Italy's building stock presents a significant proportion of older buildings, many of which with historical and cultural importance. This presents a significant challenge to meet the EU's 2050 decarbonisation target.

Italy has approximately 12.5 million residential buildings, and more than a million non-residential buildings. Considering most of them were built before 1945, many of them are protected by strict conservation laws, which may complicate any energy efficiency upgrades. Similarly, there are many residential buildings that were built between the 1960s and 1980s, a period when there were no set energy performance standards [4]. This prevalence of older buildings highlights the need to improve energy efficiency and reduce energy consumption, as many of these buildings lack energy-saving measures. The challenge of historic preservation versus energy efficiency will require innovative solutions to retrofit these buildings without compromising their architectural integrity.

Italy has developed a detailed legislative framework over the years to improve energy efficiency in buildings. One of the most effective measures is the Super bonus 110%, a fiscal incentive under the Recovery and Resilience Plan, offering tax deductions of up to 110% for energy efficiency improvements.

3.3.2 Quantification of the building stock

Figure 8 - Italy building stock in a nutshell [4]

The Italian building stock consists of approximately 14,700,000 buildings. Of these, approximately 96% are residential, while the remaining 4% are non-residential [4].

In the residential sector, there are 10 million apartment blocks and 4 million single-family houses [5]. Although apartment blocks are more difficult to renovate due to the complexity of coordination between owners, they have a greater impact on energy savings when renovated.

The non-residential buildings, demonstrate the range of activities supported by this infrastructure, including 75,150 educational buildings, 55,439 healthcare buildings, 128,957 hotels and/or restaurants, 151,828 office buildings, 189,725 buildings for wholesale and retail trade, and 9,855 buildings for other purposes [4].

Ownership is the predominant tenure status within the residential market, with 76% of homes owned by residents and 24% rented [7]. This high rate of ownership encourages greater investment in house maintenance and modernisation, particularly in energy efficiency measures, as homeowners are often more inclined to invest in improvements that increase the value of their properties and reduce ongoing energy costs.

Energy consumption is also significant: final household consumption amounts to 1,340,089 TJ of which space heating accounts for about 67%, demonstrating its predominance in energy use. Lighting and electricity account for about 13%, while water heating amounts to about 11%, cooking 6%, other end use appliances 2% and space cooling 1% [8].

3.3.3 National Building Efforts

Figure 9 - Italy's total investment in energy related renovations (2016) [13]

Analysing Italy's financial investment in the renovation of its building stock, one can observe that the investment strategy differs noticeably from that of the other countries previously analysed, particularly emphasizing on medium-sized renovations. Below follows a detailed breakdown of the investments in the residential and non-residential sectors [13]:

- **Below threshold renovations:** Residential buildings see an investment of 8,278 million Euros, significantly higher than the 1,254 million Euros allocated to non-residential properties. This level of funding indicates that routine maintenance and aesthetic updates are widespread but are not the main focus of Italy's renovation efforts.
- **Light renovations:** investments are more evenly distributed among the various types of building. Residential properties receive 6,254 million Euros, which is significantly more than the 1,806 million Euros allocated to non-residential buildings. This level of investment suggests that there is an interest in carrying out energy efficiency upgrades that do not require

major structural changes, but can offer noticeable improvements in energy performance.

- **Medium renovations:** unlike other countries, Italy invests more in medium-sized renovations. With 6,254 million Euros allocated to residential and 3,405 million Euros to non-residential buildings, placing the emphasis on this category.
- **Deep renovations:** Although lower than investments in medium-sized renovations, financing for deep renovations holds a significant weight, with 1,413 million Euros allocated to residential buildings and 584 million Euros to non-residential buildings. This significant investment, while smaller in scale, plays a crucial role in supporting critical renovations to achieve the highest levels of energy savings and modernization in Italy's building stock.

Although the investment levels of below threshold and light renovations are similar, there is an observable difference in the renovation rates. Figure 10 shows the national renovation rate by type of renovation and type of building.

Figure 10 – Italy’s renovation rate (2016) [13]

3.3.4 Prospects

The renovation of Italy’s building stock towards decarbonisation by 2050 has a detailed roadmap. By 2030, Italy aims to achieve an overall renovation rate of 2% for its building stock. This includes a 1.9% of renovation in the residential

sector, with an expected saving of 0.33 Mtoe/year and a reduction of CO₂ emissions to 32.7 million tons. For the non-residential sector, the renovation target is 2.8%, with energy savings of 0.24 Mtoe/year and a reduction in CO₂ emissions of 10.9 million tons [11].

Towards 2040, the residential sector renovation rate is expected to increase to 2.7%, while the non-residential sector will achieve a renovation rate of 2.6%. Finally, by 2050, Italy aims for an overall renovation rate of 2.6%, with more ambitious targets set for specific sectors. The residential sector is expected to achieve a renovation rate of 2.7%, renovating 66% of the building stock and achieving full decarbonisation. This implies reducing energy consumption from 32 Mtoe in 2020 to 13 Mtoe, all sourced from renewable energy sources. The non-residential sector is anticipated to be almost fully decarbonised, with CO₂ emissions reduced to 0.6 million tons and a renovation rate of 2.6% [11].

In addition to wider benefits, decarbonising the building stock has numerous socio-economic benefits. The strategy is expected to create around 79,000 new jobs per year, reduce energy imports by 13%, and cut energy bills by 15%.

Significant financial investments are required to achieve these ambitious targets. For the period between 2020 to 2030, the estimated investment needs range from 9 to 12 billion Euros annually, depending on the scenario. By 2050, promoting energy efficiency in public buildings alone will require 75 billion Euros. In addition, 50 billion Euros from the national budget will be needed to support these initiatives.

Specifically, between 2020 and 2024 municipalities had 5 to 8.8 billion Euros available to make buildings more energy efficient. For/in the period between 2020 to 2050, the investment needs in the residential sector are expected to be between 9 to 12 billion euros per year. For office buildings, the investment need is estimated at 0.7 billion Euros per year, and for other non-residential buildings, at 0.5 billion Euros per year [11].

3.4 Ireland

3.4.1 National context

In Ireland, the building stock is predominantly characterized by a mix of residential, commercial, industrial and public buildings, many of which were built before the introduction of any energy efficiency regulation. This highlights the need for comprehensive energy efficiency upgrades and the importance of reducing energy consumption [4].

Ireland’s legislative framework plays an important role in guiding the renovation and energy efficiency fits building stock. Building regulations set standards for new and existing buildings adjusted to EU directives. But Ireland has also implemented several national strategies and policies to support energy efficiency such as ‘The National Energy Efficiency Action Plan’ and ‘The Climate Action Plan’ [11].

One of the key programmes facilitating these improvements is the Better Energy Homes programme, an initiative that provides grants to homeowners for energy-saving measures. Furthermore, financial incentives such as grants from the Sustainable Energy Authority of Ireland (SEAI) support homeowners and businesses.

3.4.2 Quantification of the building stock

Figure 11 - Ireland building stock in a nutshell [4]

Ireland’s building stock accounts for more than 2.2 million buildings, including both residential and non-residential buildings. Among these, nearly 2.1 million are residential buildings, constituting approximately 95% of the total, while the remaining 5% are non-residential [4].

In the residential category, there are almost 2 million single-family houses and only 105,571 apartment blocks. Single-family homes accommodate almost 95% of the population within residential buildings [5].

The non-residential sector is diversified, including 13,925 educational buildings, 17,406 healthcare buildings, 17,406 hotels and restaurants, 6,962 office buildings, 24,369 buildings for wholesale and retail trades, and 41,776 buildings for other purposes [4].

Ownership prevails in the residential market, with 70% of homes owned by their respective occupants and 30% rented [7].

Energy consumption in households is also significant, with total final consumption reaching 128,362 TJ. Space heating is predominant and represents around 60%, highlighting its importance in energy expenditure. Water heating follows, representing around 20%, lighting and electrical uses nearly 17%, cooking around 2%, and other end-use appliances 1% [8].

3.4.3 National Building Efforts

Figure 12 - Ireland's total investment in energy related renovations (2016) [13]

Analysing Ireland's financial investment in the renovation of its building stock one can observe a distinct focus on less intensive renovations, which account for the largest part of the investments [13].

- **Below threshold renovations:** in these renovations, which achieve minimal energy savings, residential buildings receive 350 million euros, and non-residential buildings 83 million euros. This category receives significant investment, reflecting a strong emphasis on basic maintenance and minor aesthetic improvements.
- **Light renovations:** they attract the highest investment, with residential sectors receiving €624 million and non-residential sectors €128 million. The considerable funds allocated here suggest a prevalent strategy focused on achieving moderate energy efficiency improvements that do not require extensive structural changes.
- **Medium renovations:** investment levels are lower than in the light and below threshold categories. Residential buildings receive an investment of 216 million euros, and non-residential buildings 96 million euros.
- **Deep renovations:** they have the lowest investment levels, with residential buildings receiving 38 million euros and non-residential buildings 31 million euros.

Figure 13 - Ireland's renovation rate (2016) [13]

In Ireland's case, overall renovation rates are 3,9% for residential and 8% for non-residential buildings mainly due to the high incidence of below-threshold renovations, suggesting a focus on less intensive upgrades.

3.4.4 Prospects

Ireland's renovation rates are remarkably low [13]. This contrasts sharply with other countries where renovation activities, particularly those aimed at improving energy efficiency, tend to occur more frequently and encompass a larger proportion of the building stock. Raising public awareness about the benefits of energy-efficient renovations through comprehensive educational campaigns and the display of successful projects can encourage wider participation in renovation efforts.

The prospect for renovation of Ireland's Building stock aims to provide a roadmap to achieve a sustainable and energy-efficient building sector, with a particular focus on the period between 2021 to 2030. The primary objective is to significantly reduce CO₂ emissions from the built environment by 40-45% [11].

In the residential sector, the plan calls for the renovation of 500,000 homes to achieve a B2 rating or an equivalent standard. This entails renovating an average of 50,000 homes each year by 2030. The long-term targets are even more ambitious, with plans to renovate 1 million homes by 2040 and 1.5 million by 2050. In addition, local authorities will upgrade their housing stock as part of the social housing renovation programme to meet the same standards [11].

For the commercial and public sectors, at least one-third of total commercial premises will have to be upgraded to EPC level B by 2030. In addition, approximately 355,000 new dwellings are expected to be built at an A EPC level by 2030 [11].

In the residential sector, energy savings are expected to increase from 8,436 GWh in 2020 to 23,662 GWh in 2030. Similarly in the business sector, energy savings are expected to grow from 8,918 GWh in 2020 to 21,166 GWh in 2030 [11].

To support these ambitious targets, the Irish government has approved a national development plan with substantial financial allocations. Between 2020 and 2030, 4.5 billion euros have been allocated to support energy efficiency improvements in both the residential and public sectors. By 2050, a further 75 billion euros will be needed to promote energy efficiency in public buildings, along with 50 billion euros from the national budget [11].

For municipalities, 5 to 8.8 billion euros were available from 2020 and 2024 to make buildings more energy efficient and safe. Total investment needs for the residential sector are estimated at 9 to 12 billion euros per year from 2020 to 2050, with additional annual investments of 0.7 billion euros for office buildings and 0.5 billion euros for other non-residential buildings. This demonstrates Ireland's overall commitment to meeting EU goals.

3.5 Greece

3.5.1 National context

Greece's building stock, like that of the other EU countries, is characterized by residential and non-residential buildings, with a predominance of the former. Many buildings were constructed prior to the adoption of these energy efficiency standards (before 1980), when energy efficiency was not a primary issue in building design. Consequently, there is an urgent need for energy efficiency upgrades.

The Greek legislative framework addresses these challenges through the Greek Building Regulation (KENAK), which sets energy performance requirements, promoting energy efficiency, and Energy Performance Certificates (EPCs) are required for transactions.

A key initiative is the “Exoikonomo-Afternomo” programme, providing financial incentives for energy-savings measures such as insulation and efficient heating systems. These initiatives have led to significant energy savings and improvements in building performance.

In addition to these measures, Greece has launched several other key initiatives to further support its decarbonisation goals. The “ELEKTRA” programme is focused on the energetic modernisation of public buildings, with a substantial funding allocation of 640 million euros. This programme is part of Pillar 1- Green Transition of the National Recovery and Resilience Plan “Greece 2.0”. Similarly, the Energy Upgrade of Central Administration & OTA Buildings Programme, aims to improve the energy efficiency of building management by central administration and local government authorities, with a budget of 7 million euros.

These programmes, together with the regulatory frameworks and incentives, constitute a comprehensive approach to achieve Greece's ambitious decarbonisation plan.

3.5.2 Quantification of the building stock

Figure 14 - Greece building stock in a nutshell [4]

Greece’s building stock comprises over 4.24 million structures, including both residential and non-residential buildings. Of these, over 3.63 million are residential buildings, which represent approximately 86% of the total, with the remaining 14% being non-residential (0.604 million buildings) [4].

In the residential sector, there are nearly 2.5 million single-family homes and less than 1.2 million apartment blocks [5].

The non-residential sector is diverse, including 14,756 educational buildings, 7,888 healthcare buildings, 52,320 hotels and restaurants, 5,366 office buildings, 464,173 wholesale and retail trade buildings, and 50,369 buildings for other purposes [4].

In the residential market, ownership is predominant, with 74% of homes owned by their respective occupants and 26% rented [7].

Household energy consumption is significant, with total final consumption reaching 178,592 TJ. Space heating accounts for approximately 53% of this usage, underlining its importance in energy expenditure. Lighting and electrical uses reach 20% of consumption, water heating makes up approximately 14%,

cooking around 9%, and space cooling 4%, reflecting Greece’s climatic needs [8].

3.5.3 National Building Efforts

Figure 15 - Greece’s total investment in energy related renovations (2016) [13]

The analysis of Greece's financial investment in the renovation of its building stock reveals a strong emphasis on medium-sized renovations, reflecting their significant role in the country's approach to improving energy efficiency and modernizing their building stock [13].

- **Below threshold renovations**: these renovations see considerable investment and represent a substantial part of the renovation efforts. Residential buildings receive 1,097 million euros, while non-residential buildings receive 306 million euros.
- **Light renovations**: investments in light renovations amount to 419 million euros for residential and 440 million euros for non-residential buildings.
- **Medium renovations**: they receive significant investment, with 601 million euros allocated to residential buildings and a similar amount of 610 million euros to non-residential buildings. This demonstrates the importance given to medium-sized renovations, which are designed to achieve substantial energy savings of between 30% and 60%.

- **Deep Renovations:** they represent the smallest investment category, with 131 million euros allocated to residential buildings and 100 million euros to non-residential buildings.

Figure 16 - Greece's renovation rate (2016) [13]

To develop a forward-looking perspective on the renovation prospects for Greece's building stock it is crucial to understand the current renovation rates. The total renovation rate in the residential sector is 8.9% and in the non-residential sector 10.6%. This highlights the high incidence of below threshold and light renovations, which involves fewer intensive interventions. While these renovations are essential to maintain and slightly improve the condition of the buildings, they typically offer limited energy savings.

In the case of medium-sized and deep renovations, the rates are significantly lower, but not sufficient to meet the energy savings necessary to significantly reduce overall energy consumption and environmental impact.

3.5.4 Prospects

Greece's decarbonisation milestone expectations by 2030 include the renovation of 12% to 15% of its buildings and the reduction of final energy demand in buildings by 8% in comparison to 2015 levels. This includes upgrading 23% of the building envelope in residential buildings and 9% in non-residential buildings. Particular attention will also be paid to reducing oil use in buildings, with a switch to 47% of gas boilers, the introduction of air-source heat pumps, and an 11% reduction in traditional biomass combustion [11].

The goals for 2040 include a more substantial reduction in energy demand, aiming for a 20 to 28% decrease in comparison to 2015. The upgrades will extend to between 36 to 42% of residential building envelopes and 14 to 16% of heating needs met by air-source heat pumps, 20% by gas boilers and 83 to 96% by solar thermal heaters.

Looking to 2050, Greece aims to reduce final energy demands in buildings by 28 - 40% compared to 2015. The retrofit targets include 45 to 49% of residential building envelopes and 19 to 20% of non-residential building envelopes. The heating system will further shift to 15 to 50% air-source heat pumps, 14 to 64% gas boilers, and 83 to 92% solar thermal heaters, with the elimination of electric boilers.

The energetic improvement of 15% of Greek homes from 2021-2030, along with other energy efficiency improvements, is expected to boost the national economy. This initiative is expected to increase the national added value by approximately 8 billion euros and create and maintain 22,000 new full-time jobs annually. In addition, the income of employees in related sectors is expected to increase by about 3.4 billion euros.

To achieve these ambitious goals, substantial investments are needed. By 2030, Greece will need around 10 billion euros per year to support these renovations. This investment need is expected to increase to 20 billion euros per year by 2050.

3.6 Lithuania

3.6.1 National context

Lithuania's building stock consists of a substantial proportion of older structures, reflecting the nation's historical and architectural heritage. Most (nearly 90%) of the buildings constructed in Lithuania before 1940 were built of wood. Many new buildings were built and refurbished in the 1990s, but many wooden buildings remain, meaning most of which lack modern energy-saving technologies, leading to high energy consumption and inefficiency.

Lithuania has a building stock of 600,000 buildings. To date, only about 4% of apartment buildings have been renovated while the vast majority are in urgent need of upgrading to reduce energy consumption [11].

Over the years, Lithuania has witnessed several energy transitions, which support the EU's climate neutrality goals. Although Lithuania has not met the 2020 final energy consumption target, further measures are needed.

Lithuania has adopted specific policies and initiatives to improve energy efficiency, such as the ‘Multi-apartment Building Renovation (Modernization) Programme’ approved in 2004 whose main goal is to reduce thermal energy use in multi-apartment buildings, built before 1993 [11].

The European Bank for Reconstruction and Development (EBRD) is providing a €67.5 million loan to support the renovation of multi-apartment residential buildings, planning to improve the energy performance of residential buildings in Lithuania by at least 40% and achieve a minimum energy performance class C.

3.6.2 Quantification of the building stock

Figure 17 - Lithuania building stock in a nutshell [4]

Lithuania’s building stock includes more than 0.59 million structures, with both residential and non-residential buildings. Nearly 0.51 million buildings are residential accounting for less than 87% of the total, while the remaining 13% are non-residential [4].

In the residential sector, there are nearly 0.4 million single-family houses and 107,606 apartment blocks [5].

The non-residential sector features a range of building types, including 5,335 educational buildings, 889 healthcare buildings, 2,225 hotels and restaurants,

35,572 office buildings, 28,457 buildings for wholesale and retail trade, and 6,225 buildings for other purposes [4].

Home ownership is common in the residential market, with 89% of homes occupied by owners and 11% rented. This high rate of ownership encourages investment in home maintenance and modernisation, especially in energy efficiency, as owners are likely to make improvements that increase property value and reduce energy expenses [7].

Household energy consumption is substantial, amounting to a total final consumption of 68,228 TJ. Space heating is the largest use, accounting for about 68% of this energy, highlighting its importance. Lighting and electrical consumes around 14%, water heating accounts for about 12%, cooking about 6%, and space cooling is minimal, reflecting Lithuania’s diverse climate needs [8].

3.6.3 National Building Efforts

Figure 18 - Lithuania’s total investments in energy related renovations (2016) [13]

In Lithuania, the distribution of financial investments among different types of building renovations provides key insights into the country's priorities and challenges in improving building energy efficiency. Although there is a significant commitment to medium-sized renovations, most investments continue to be destined to below threshold and light renovations [13]:

- **Below Threshold Renovations:** the residential sector receives 199 million euros, while the non-residential sector receives 36 million euros. This high level of investment reflects a strong focus on maintaining the conditions of existing buildings rather than improving energy efficiency.
- **Light Renovations:** they are also the subject of considerable investment. The residential sector attracts 147 million euros, while the non-residential sector attracts 30 million Euros.
- **Medium-sized Renovations:** despite not being the highest in financial terms, medium-sized renovations still account for a significant portion of the investment, with 83 million euros in the residential sector and 43 million euros in the non-residential sector.
- **Deep Renovations:** the least invested category, deep renovations, receives 7 million euros in residential and 3 million euros in non-residential sectors.

Figure 19 - Lithuania's renovation rate (2016) [13]

Knowing renovation rates and understanding Lithuania's trends in the scope and depth of the renovations undertaken in residential and non-residential buildings is important to discuss national building efforts.

The total renovation rate for the residential sector is 8.9% and for the non-residential 6.2%, highlighting the focus on more superficial upgrades to maintain

the buildings and provide small energy improvements. More intensive and light renovations are less frequent. Implementing or strengthening policies that require or incentivize deeper renovations along with targeted incentives for medium and deep renovations could make these options more attractive to property owners and push the market towards greater energy savings.

3.6.4 Prospects

Lithuania's vision to decarbonise its building stock by 2050 includes significant reduction in primary energy consumption (PEC) and CO₂ emissions, as well as ambitious renovation targets and investment strategies.

By 2030, Lithuania aims to reduce its annual PEC to 34,759 GWh, which means 85% of the current levels. Excluding renewable energy sources (RES), the PEC target is 19,865 GWh (75%). CO₂ emissions are expected to fall to 4003 ktCO₂, equating to 76% of current levels. The goal is to renovate 99,281 buildings, representing 17% of the total building stock. Upgrading more than 5,000 apartments and approximately 960,000 m² of public buildings to energy class C is expected to save 1.9 TWh and 0.19 TWh of energy. [11]

For 2040, the annual PEC target is set at 25,888 GWh, a 39% reduction. Primary energy consumption (PEC) excluding RES remains at 19,865 GWh, also representing a 39% reduction. CO₂ emissions are expected to decrease to 2,108 ktCO₂, or 40% of current levels. The number of renovated buildings will increase to 225,421, covering 43% of the building stock. Primary energy savings and CO₂ reductions will be most significant in single dwellings (39% and 30% respectively), followed by the multifamily buildings (25% and 24%), other non-residential buildings (20% and 24%) and industrial buildings (16% and 22%).

By 2050, Lithuania aims to drastically reduce energy consumption and CO₂ emissions. The annual PEC is set at 16,162 GWh, a 60% reduction from 2020 levels. CO₂ emissions are expected to reach zero ktCO₂, indicating complete decarbonisation. The number of renovated buildings is expected to rise to 436,008, covering 74% of the building stock. Achieving higher energy classes (A+, A++, or NZEB) may encounter technical constraints as it requires high air tightness which is usually difficult to achieve in old buildings.

Investments in building renovations are expected to yield significant economic benefits. Every 1 million euros invested is expected to create between 19 and 37 jobs per year. In addition, each euro invested is estimated to increase Lithuania's GDP by 0.5 euros and provide health benefits valued at 0.325 euros.

Achieving these goals will require financial investment, estimated at 60 billion euros up to 2050. This includes an annual investment of 1.1 billion euros by 2030, increasing to 3.1 billion euros by 2050. The expected benefits over this

period are estimated at about 75.3 billion euros. Existing funding sources will become insufficient by 2030, necessitating the launch of new funding sources. European Union funds, including renewal initiatives in the 2021-2027 programmes and the European Green Deal Investment Plan, will be crucial. Public funds are expected to cover more than 30% of total investment needs, and new financing solutions are anticipated for the owner's contributions to renovation costs.

3.7 Slovakia

3.7.1 National context

Buildings have an impact on final energy consumption in Slovakia estimated at 40%. A systematic approach to building renovation was adopted in the early 1990s, when it was found that buildings older than 30 years built on a large-scale, particularly between 1960 and 1992, all showed inadequate thermal protection of building structures and significant wear and tear of technical equipment, which needed to be replaced as soon as possible.

Slovakia has an appropriate legislative framework and has implemented efficient financial mechanisms; it is leading the renovation of multi-apartment buildings in the European Union. However, the ambitious goals of decarbonisation of building stock by 2050 require more changes.

Slovakia employs strategies to improve its building stock that are aligned with the UE regulatory framework. The Energy Performance of Building Directive (EPBD) establishes requirements for energy performance certificates (EPCs), nearly-zero energy buildings (NZEBs) and regular inspections.

In Slovakia there are different and specific measures to implement the renovation plan, aiming to promote cost-effective deep renovation of buildings, target less energy-efficient buildings and energy poverty, target public buildings and use incentives for the use of smart technologies.

3.7.2 Quantification of the building stock

Figure 20 - Slovakia building stock in a nutshell [4]

Slovakia’s buildings stock includes more than 1,221,437 residential and non-residential buildings. Almost 1.2 million are residential buildings and 8,564 non-residential buildings [4].

In the residential sector, there are almost 0.967 million single-family houses and 0.246 million apartment blocks [5].

The non-residential sector includes a variety of buildings, including 856 education buildings, 1,223 healthcare buildings, 1,223 hotels and restaurants, 2,446 office buildings, 1,835 buildings for wholesale and retail trade, and 978 buildings for other purposes [4].

Home ownership is prevalent in the residential market, with 93% of homes owned by their occupants and 7% rented. This high rate of ownership promotes investment in home maintenance and upgrading, particularly in energy efficiency, as homeowners are more likely to invest in improvements that increase property value and reduce energy costs [7].

Energy consumption in households is significant, with total final consumption reaching 124,206 TJ. Space heating is the dominant use, accounting for around 75% of this energy, underlining its importance. Water heating accounts for

approximately 12%, lighting and electricity uses around 9%, and cooking approximately 4%, reflecting the diverse climatic needs across Slovakia [8].

3.7.3 National Building Efforts

Figure 21 - Slovakia's total investment in energy related renovations (2016) [13]

Financial investment in Slovakia's building renovation sector shows a diverse allocation of funds, where light and below threshold renovations have a larger volume, but medium renovations carry a substantial weight [13]:

- **Below Threshold Renovations:** they involve investments of 339 million euros for residential buildings and 90 million euros for non-residential buildings.
- **Light Renovations:** with the highest investment at 385 million euros in residential buildings and 135 million euros in non-residential buildings, light renovations indicate a strong preference for small-scale upgrades.
- **Medium Renovations:** see a notable investment of 193 million euros in residential and a greater investment of 227 million euros in non-residential sectors. The high investment, especially in non-residential buildings, reflects the recognition of the significant impact these renovations can have on reducing overall energy consumption and operating costs.
- **Deep Renovations:** Despite their maximum energy saving potential, deep renovations receive the lowest level of investment, with 16 million euros allocated to residential buildings and 37 million Euros to non-

residential buildings. This discrepancy highlights the challenges and costs associated with complete overhauls, which often involve complete system replacements and extensive structural changes.

Figure 22 - Slovakia’s renovation rate (2016) [13]

As Slovakia continues to refine and advance its energy policies, it is crucial to understand the distribution of renovation activities within its building stock is critical. By examining the current renovation rate and understanding the trends in the scope and depth of the renovations carried out in residential and non-residential properties, one can gain valuable insights into how the country might better align its building practices.

The overall renovation rates are 9.7% for residential and 14.6% for non-residential buildings [13]. Below threshold and light renovations represent the bulk of renovation activities, as they focus on superficial updates that maintain building functionality, providing moderate energy improvements. More intensive renovations with rates for medium renovations and deep renovations represent the most substantial opportunities for energy savings, being much lower than the other renovations.

3.7.4 Prospects

The goal to decarbonise Slovakia’s building stock by 2050 includes significant milestones and strategic actions during the span of three decades: 2030, 2040 and 2050. The vision includes energy consumption targets, CO₂ emissions reduction goals, renovation aims and necessary investments to achieve said objectives.

By 2030, Slovakia aims to reduce energy consumption to 39.9 TWh and achieve cumulative energy savings of 10,518 GWh. This period will see CO₂ emissions fall to 5.5 MtCO₂, marking a 61% reduction compared to 1990 levels. All multi-family buildings are expected to be renovated, with 29% of residential buildings undergoing deep renovations [11].

By 2040 the expected goal is to reduce energy consumption to 33.6 TWh and increase cumulative energy savings to 18,368 GWh. CO₂ emissions are expected to decrease to 3.4 MtCO₂, a 74% reduction from 1990 levels. By this time, all single-family buildings will be expected to have been renovated, marking a significant step towards complete renovation of Slovakia's building stock.

Looking to 2050, the energy consumption target is set at 28.3 TWh, which represents a 40% reduction from 2020 levels. Cumulative energy savings are expected to reach 19,006 GWh. CO₂ emissions will be dramatically reduced to 1.8 MtCO₂, achieving an 87% reduction compared to 1990 levels and a 79% reduction compared to 2020. Furthermore, electricity and heat supply will be decarbonised by 50%, with the goal of renovating all buildings by this year.

The pace of renovations in the non-residential building sector has been slow, primarily financed by Structural Funds (ESIF) and private investment. By 2050, carbon emissions from gas will be reduced by 25% and renewable energy sources in buildings are expected to increase by 10% every five years, reaching a 50% increase from 2025 to 2050. New buildings constructed by 2050 will have a net zero impact on emissions. The distribution of renovation types is expected to be 40% deep renovation (over 60% primary energy savings), 10% at Nearly-Zero Energy Building (NZEB) levels, 40% medium renovation (savings of 30-60%), and 10% light renovation (energy savings 3-10%).

Investments in the renovation of Slovakia's building stock are crucial. Currently, the annual investment rate is 900 M€, but the future requirement is estimated to be between 1.1 billion and 1.2 billion euros per year, reaching 1.3 billion euros per year between 2026 and 2031. The cumulative investment requirement by 2050 is expected to be 22.8 billion euros, 17.3 billion of which for residential buildings and 5.5 billion for non-residential buildings. The financial resources will come from the Multiannual Financial Framework 2021-2027, which provides 750 M€ for residential buildings and 367.5 M€ for public buildings. Further fundings will come from the Recovery and Resilience Facility, including 300 M€ for improving the energy efficiency of family homes, 130 M€ for the renovation of historical and monumental protected public buildings and 200 M€ for the improvement of public buildings.

4 Regulatory framework for Energy Efficiency in the European Union

The persistent energy efficiency (EE) gap has been a focal point in European energy policy debates, emphasizing the need for strategic interventions to exploit the "win-win" opportunities it presents. This gap refers to the difference between cost-effective energy savings potential and the savings achieved. Since the 1990s, the European Union has recognised the importance of this issue, leading to the implementation of numerous programmes aimed at removing barriers to optimal investments in energy efficiency [14]

The approach to addressing the energy efficiency gap in the EU has evolved significantly over the years, influenced by a mixture of scientific insights and stakeholder consultations. Initially dominated by the perspectives of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (STEM) disciplines, EU energy policy has traditionally been driven by a narrative that prioritises technological development. This orientation has sometimes overshadowed the importance of social and human factors, which are crucial in shaping energy consumption patterns and the public's engagement with energy policies [14].

However, recent shifts in policy-making paradigms have begun to acknowledge the critical role of social sciences, especially conduct-related sciences. These disciplines provide valuable insights into the human dimensions of energy use, emphasizing that energy efficiency is not merely a technological challenge but also a behavioural one. The integration of behavioural sciences into energy policy reflects the growing acknowledgement that understanding and influencing consumer behaviour is essential to closing the EE gap [14].

In response to these complexities, the European Union has developed multiple key legislative frameworks [15] to guide and enhance energy efficiency across Member States.

4.1 Energy Performance of Buildings Directive

The Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) is a key component of the EU's strategy to improve energy efficiency and reduce carbon emissions in its member states. Established to address the significant energy consumption and emissions attributed to the building sector, the EPBD sets out comprehensive requirements for improving the energy performance of both new and existing buildings. By setting different mandating standards for energy certification, renovation strategies, and the integration of renewable energy sources, the EPBD aims to create a more sustainable and energy-efficient built environment [16].

The Revised Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (Recast EPBD), as part of the “Fit for 55” package, was adopted in April 2024. It offers a robust framework designed and a set of ambitious measures to significantly reduce the decarbonisation gap in buildings and realign the EU to the ambitious 2030 and 2050 climate targets. The effectiveness of the EPBD depends not only on its legislative strength, but also on its implementation in the Member States. With the transposition period starting in the summer of 2024, Member States will enter a crucial two-year phase focused on adapting national policies to meet the directive’s targets [17].

The recast EPBD not only strengthens immediate policy measures, but also aligns with a broader 2050 vision for the complete decarbonisation of the EU building stock. This is reflected in the new role and structure of the National Building Renovation Plans (NBRPs), which are set to play a pivotal role in achieving these long-term goals. The recast EPBD transforms NBRP into a comprehensive and strategic tool that goes beyond simple planning. It is now designed to support the full decarbonisation of the national building stocks by 2050, integrating a robust social focus that includes key indicators on energy poverty and workforce skills development. The plans are intended to serve not only as planning tools, but also as dynamic tools to report and assess progress toward decarbonisation targets [17].

To standardize and streamline the process, the recast EPBD introduces an EU-wide template that Member States are required to follow when drafting their NBRPs. This template specifies the structure and content of the plans, including a list of mandatory and optional indicators. This standardized approach aids Member States in their planning activities and facilitates the monitoring and evaluation tasks of the European Commission, ensuring consistency and comparability across countries.

By further integrating the NBRP with broader EU energy policies, the EPBD recast aligns the renovation plan process with the cycles of the National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) [17]. Like NECPs, the preparation of NBRPs will follow a three-step process:

- Submission of the draft plan by Member States.
- Assessment of the draft plan by the Commission, which may include country-specific recommendations.
- Submission of the final plan by Member States, considering the Commission’s feedback.

This synchronization not only ensures methodological consistency, but also aligns the timing between NBRPs and NECPs, facilitating a coordinated approach to energy and climate policy across the EU. The first NBRP cycle in 2025/2026 will set the precedent for this integrated approach.

Figure 23 - Requirements and deadlines, linked to NBRP and NECP cycles until 2034 [17]

4.2 Energy Efficiency Directive

The Energy Efficiency Directive (EED) is a fundamental component of the European Union's strategy to enhance energy efficiency and reduce energy consumption across all member states. In 2018, as part of the broader 'Clean energy for all Europeans package', the directive underwent significant amendments to strengthen its impact and broaden its scope. These amendments introduced updated energy efficiency targets, aiming for an improvement of at least 32.5% by 2030 based on 2007 projections, and expanded the energy savings obligation, requiring EU countries to achieve specific annual energy savings from 2021 to 2030. This robust framework was established to ensure consistent and measurable reductions in energy consumption, supporting the EU's broader environmental and sustainability objectives [18]. A recast of the EED Directive was approved in 2023 [19].

On this basis, the Directive saw further revisions under the 'Fit for 55' package in July 2021, aimed at reducing net greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030 compared to 1990 levels. This package proposed increasing the energy efficiency target to 9% compared to the 2020 baseline, highlighting the crucial role of energy efficiency in the EU's climate strategy. Finally, in response to geopolitical changes and the urgent need to reduce dependence on external fossil fuel sources, particularly from Russia, the REPowerEU plan proposed to further increase the energy efficiency target to 13%, highlighting energy efficiency as a key sustainable strategy to improve the EU's energy independence [18].

These continuous improvements of the EED reflect the importance of having structured and enforceable energy efficiency frameworks that guide Member States towards significant reductions in energy use. Furthermore, the Directive emphasizes the importance of monitoring and evaluating progress, ensuring that all EU countries are accountable and transparent in their efforts to improve energy efficiency. This includes detailed reporting and the integration of energy efficiency targets into National Energy and Climate Plans (NECPs) [19].

4.3 Fit for 55 Package

The "Fit for 55" package is a comprehensive set of legislative measures adopted by the European Union to align its policies with the ambitious goal of reducing greenhouse gas emissions by at least 55% by 2030, compared to 1990 levels, ultimately aiming for climate neutrality by 2050. This initiative is part of the European Green Deal and represents a crucial cornerstone of the EU's climate action and energy policy [20].

The "Fit for 55" package reviews and updates existing EU legislation and introduces new initiatives in a broad range of areas including climate, energy, transport, and buildings. It seeks to provide a balanced and coherent framework that ensures that all EU policies contribute effectively to the climate objectives. The package is not only about reducing emissions but also about improving energy efficiency, increasing the use of renewable energy sources, and ensuring a fair transition for all sectors and regions within the EU [21]:

- **Energy Efficiency**: The package includes ambitious proposals to increase energy efficiency in all sectors. It builds on the principles set out in the Energy Efficiency Directive and introduces stricter regulations and targets to ensure more substantial energy savings.
- **Renewable Energy**: Increasing the share of renewable energy is another key pillar of the package. It aims to revise the Renewable Energy Directive to set higher targets for the use of renewable energy, supporting the EU's transition from fossil fuels to more sustainable energy sources.
- **Emission Reductions**: The package also involves a significant revamp of the EU Emissions Trading System (ETS), expanding its scope and tightening emission allowances to ensure more effective market-based incentives for reducing greenhouse gas emissions.
- **Sector-Specific Actions**: Specific measures target emissions from new cars and vans, aiming for substantial reductions by 2030 and moving towards zero emissions in the following years. Similarly, the package addresses emissions from aviation and maritime transport, promoting cleaner technologies and fuels.

- **Social Climate Fund:** Recognizing the social implications of these transitions, the package proposes the establishment of a Social Climate Fund. This fund is intended to support citizens in managing the transition, helping to cover the costs of energy upgrades and ensuring that the shift towards a greener economy is socially fair.

4.4 The Renovation Wave

The Renovation Wave is a European Union initiative designed to increase the rate and depth of renovations in the EU's building stock to improve energy efficiency and reduce overall carbon emissions. This initiative is a key component of the European Green Deal, which aims to double renovation rates over the next decade and ensure that 35 million buildings are renovated by 2030. The overall aim is to meet the EU's ambitious climate targets while tackling energy poverty and stimulating job creation [22].

A key aspect of the Renovation Wave is its commitment to alleviating energy poverty by prioritizing renovations in vulnerable communities to help reduce energy bills, improve living conditions, and increase overall quality of life. Economically, the initiative is expected to create up to 160,000 green jobs in the construction sector by 2030, helping Europe's post-COVID-19 economic recovery [22].

The Renovation Wave is supported by regulatory revisions, including updates to the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive, and financial mechanisms such as public and private funding, green mortgages, and energy performance contracting. These measures are designed to encourage large-scale, effective renovations.

4.5 National regulations in each country

4.6 Spain

Spain's Long-Term Renovation Strategy outlines a comprehensive policy framework within an implementation plan, targeting the renovation of 1,2 million dwellings between 2021 and 2030. The goal is to increase the annual renovation rate from 30,000 to 300,000 units.

In the residential sector, the strategy aims for a 99% reduction in greenhouse gas emissions by 2050 compared to current levels, using a combination of public and private investments. This plan is aligned with various national and local strategies, plans and frameworks.

The legislative measures include:

- Updating the Technical Construction Code: The energy saving document is revised to incorporate NZEB requirements and introduce new indicators and criteria for both new and existing buildings.
- Revising the Regulation on Thermal Installations in Buildings: Enhances the qualification standards for professionals and companies.
- Implementing new self-consumption regulations: Simplified schemes for households to offset or sell surplus energy and facilities collective energy sharing among neighbouring buildings.
- Introducing new regulations for Energy Communities
- Requiring energy assessment reports: Mandatory for residential buildings over 50 years old, ensuring regular evaluations.
- Establishing a Centralized Certification Register: Maintain statistics on the energy rating status of the building stock.

4.7 Portugal

The Long-Term Renovation strategy aims to transform existing buildings into ones with NZEB efficiency by 2050, focusing on reducing emissions, enhancing thermal comfort, combating energy poverty, improving indoor air quality, and addressing issues of safety and efficient management of material resources, water efficiency, and environmental performance. The strategy is based on three main pillars: improving quality of life to reduce energy poverty and increase thermal comfort and indoor air quality, fostering economic growth opportunities, and achieving energy and climate goals.

To achieve said goals, Portugal will adapt its legislation to promote energy renovation. These adaptations will include:

- Redirecting tax revenues to improve the environmental and energy performance of buildings.
- Introducing tax incentives for energy efficiency and renewable energy production for self-consumption.
- Setting more ambitious mandatory regulatory minimums (MEPS).
- Aligning regulatory requirements related to energy performance with energy instruments.
- Addressing “split incentives” by balancing benefits between tenants and owners.
- Simplifying audit and licensing processes.
- Creating a legal and financial framework that strengthens the role of owners’ associations in regulating renovations.

4.8 Italy

Italy's Long-Term Renovation Strategy provides a detailed assessment of the country's building stock. The main goal is to achieve complete decarbonisation of the residential sector and almost complete decarbonisation of the non-residential sector by 2050. It is estimated that to achieve this, two-thirds of existing buildings must be renovated in the next 30 years. This will require increasing the current renovation rate from 0,85% to 2% over the next decade and tripling it for the 2030-2050 period.

While the targets set for 2030 seem feasible due to the strict policy framework, especially for the residential sector, achieving the 2050 objectives poses a significant challenge. The legislative measures include:

- Tax deductions for building renovations: All taxpayers may receive deductions for interventions in existing buildings, with an estimate total of 45.4 billion euros.
- Introduction of a feed-in tariff to encourage energy communities, renewable energy self-consumption, and the promotion of nearly zero energy districts.

4.9 Ireland

Ireland's Long-Term Renovation Strategy's key milestones are aligned with those from the Climate Change Action Plan and the National Energy and Climate Plan, focusing on reducing CO₂ emissions in the built environment through the refurbishment of residential, public, and commercial buildings. The strategy aims to reduce CO₂ emissions from the built environment by 40-45% compared to 2030 projections by retrofitting 1.5 million buildings by 2050. It also aims to upgrade 500,000 buildings to EPC level B2 by 2030. The legislative measures include:

- Advanced performance requirements: Creating a rapid transition to low-carbon heating systems in new homes.
- Retrofit taskforce: A cross-departmental and cross-agency taskforce was established to oversee the design and development of a new retrofit delivery model for the residential sector.
- Further regulations from 2022 to phase out the installation of oil boilers and the installation of gas boilers.
- Potential use of tax incentives to simulate the demand for residential energy efficiency improvements.
- Code of practice for residential energy-efficient upgrades.

4.10 Greece

Greece's long-term Renovation Strategy envisages an increase in energy-saving by increasing the number of renovated buildings, and the number of upgraded building envelopes and technical building systems. According to the European Commission, further evidence is needed to support the practical achievement of the proposed milestones. The strategy sets the target of upgrading 12-15% of buildings. The legislative measures include:

- Mandatory installation of solar thermal systems in new buildings.
- New buildings must meet the minimum energy performance requirements (class B), energy new building of the public sector should be NZEB.
- The establishment of smart readiness indicator (SRI) of the buildings, which express the ability to adapt the operation of the building unit to the needs of the tenants and the network, and the possibility to improve its energy efficiency and overall performance.
- The inclusion of Building Automation and Controls in buildings requires the establishment of automation and control systems in non-residential buildings with heating systems or combining heating and ventilation systems with a high output power.

4.11 Lithuania

Lithuania's Long-term Renovation strategy aims to fully decarbonise its building stock by 2050 through the following measures:

- Renovate 74% of the building stock.
- Reduce annual primary energy consumption by 60%.
- Eliminate annual primary energy consumption from fossil fuels.
- Achieve a 100% reduction in CO₂ emission.

At a legislative level:

- National Energy Independence Strategy: Updated in 2018, it includes targets and support for 2030 provided in all dimensions. Targets for research, innovation and competitiveness in the decarbonisation dimensions are focused on reducing energy consumption, increasing renewable energy usage, and improving energy efficiency across various sectors, including building renovations.

- Public Investment and Development Agency: This agency provides loans for the installation of solar power systems, supporting the broader legislative framework to improve energy efficiency and reduce dependence on fossil fuels.
- Energy Efficiency Financing Platform: Loans for small renovation projects.
- Financial support for prosumers aims to increase electricity production from renewable sources and to turn half of all electricity consumers into prosumers by 2050.
- The renovation/modernization of multi-apartment buildings is expected to meet the targets.

4.12 Slovakia

Slovakia's long-term renovation strategy is aligned with the Integrated National Energy and Climate Plan for 2030 and the Low Carbon Strategy for Development. It specifically targets the residential sector, aiming to renovate all multifamily buildings by 2030 and all single-family buildings by 2040. According to the European Commission, the strategy does not clearly distinguish between existing and new measures and appears to continue many of the existing measures in the building sector.

At a legislative level:

- The new Slovak Construction Act and Spatial Planning Act, aims to modernize and accelerate building procedures. They combine zoning and construction procedures into one streamlined process, boost digitalization, and shift some responsibilities and decision-making powers from local governments to the state government. This change aims to address past inefficiencies and long approval times in the construction sector, making building processes faster and more transparent.
- Housing Development Programme: Includes a grant for insulation of a family house.
- State Housing Development Fund: These are direct subsidies for individual houses.
- Other financial and legislative support is provided in Slovakia to promote building renovations, such as grants for energy-efficient home improvements, loans for renewable energy installations, and financial aid for renovations aimed at reducing energy consumption and emissions, including small electricity generation installations and heat generators that cover household energy needs.

5 FINANCIAL SCHEMES

To achieve the ambitious goal set in The Climate Target Plan 2030 [15], to reduce the overall greenhouse gas emissions from buildings by around 60% it is essential to encourage building renovation. Although this need has been identified, the current rate of renovation and investment in building renovations across Europe is still not sufficient. Recognising this, the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) highlights the key role of financial mechanisms, incentives, and the active involvement of financial institutions in national building renovation plans. These efforts are crucial to increase the renovation activities needed for a substantial reduction in energy consumption and greenhouse gas emissions.

There is a significant financing gap in current renovation investments - in 2021 the accumulated investment in building renovation was 41% less than the needed one to ensure the achievement of 2050 targets [12]. Traditional financing schemes are not sufficient to unlock the private investment [19]. The analysis reported below explores a full range of financing options, covering traditional financial schemes such as loans, grants and financial incentives as well as innovative financial schemes like on-bill and on-tax financing, energy performance contracting and green debt.

5.1 Traditional financial instruments

This section discusses traditional financing instruments [6], which are already in place and implemented in many Member States. Although these instruments are well-established and broadly used, they often lack the specificity needed to address the unique challenges associated with energy renovation. In exploring these traditional financial schemes, we will evaluate their main aspects, strengths and limits together with examples from different Member States.

5.1.1 Loans

Loans are a form of debt financing by which financial institutions provide liquidity and direct access to capital, which can be more relevant for energy efficiency measures associated with high upfront costs, especially in deep renovation projects. While loans are a mature financing scheme, meaning that they are well understood and widely accepted by society, they are not without limitations, particularly when applied to energy renovations:

- Financial institutions have developed strict lending criteria to ensure that loans are extended to borrowers who are most likely to repay. This practice may exclude vulnerable consumers who could be most in need

of energy renovations as inefficient buildings are often linked to energy poverty.

- Typically, energy renovation loans are classified as “consumers loans,” which tend to carry higher interest rates [6]. This classification comes from the perception that the borrower is consuming goods without obtaining significant economic benefits, thus increasing the perceived risk of non-repayment.
- The perception of high risk associated with energy efficiency loans limits their attractiveness to financial institutions [6]. Factors hindering market uptake include high transaction costs relative to project size and inadequate financing conditions to support deeper renovations over the necessary timeframes.

To address these challenges and promote the uptake of energy renovation loans, several interventions have been implemented to mitigate the inherent risks perceived by financial institutions and to make the lending process more favourable to consumers undertaking energy-efficient renovations:

- International financial institutions and national governments have collaborated to offer loans with more attractive terms through public-private partnerships. These efforts aim to reduce the financial burden on borrowers and encourage more substantial investments in energy efficiency.
- Implementation of soft loan schemes: these involve favourable conditions for borrowers, such as below-average market rates, longer payback periods, and loan guarantees that cover initial losses due to non-payment. For example, the “KredEx Renovation loan for apartment buildings” in Estonia provides long-term loans at low-interest rate specifically for the energy-efficient renovation of old residential buildings.
- State-owned Investment Banks like Germany's Kreditanstalt für Wiederaufbau (KfW) and the UK's Green Investment Bank (GIB) have been instrumental in filling financing gaps for energy renovations. By providing funding and creating trust for energy-efficient projects, these banks facilitate additional private financing and support the greening of national economies.

5.1.2 Grants

Grants are essential public financing instruments to facilitate energy renovations, especially when addressing the significant upfront costs associated with such projects. Mostly supported by government programmes at local or state level, often drawing on EU funds, grants provide crucial financial support to homeowners under specific conditions. However, while grants are the most cost-effective method for consumers to finance home renovation, insufficient

communication, stringent capital requirements, and bureaucratic obstacles can pose challenges to using these funds. Furthermore, grants have inherent limitations and undesirable market effects [23]:

- Their main limitation is represented by budgetary constraints since they are typically linked to public resources and therefore cannot offer a sustainable solution nor support large-scale market uptake programmes.
- There is evidence that grants can lead to undesirable market effects. Consumers may lose the incentive to seek the most cost-efficient renovation solutions, while suppliers may increase prices, exploiting the availability of subsidies to maximize their profits, regardless of actual costs.

In the EU context, grants have supported a range of energy efficiency projects, from single appliance upgrades to extensive renovations that include multiple energy-saving measures. Examples across Europe, from the Czech Republic's "New Green Savings Programme" to Greece's "Saving Energy at Home" programme, illustrate the diverse application and significant impact of grants in promoting energy-efficient renovations.

To maximise the effectiveness of grant schemes, it is essential to integrate them into a broader policy mix that includes other fiscal and financial instruments, potentially improving their impact and sustainability.

5.1.3 Tax incentives

Tax incentives are a powerful tool for promoting energy efficiency in the building sector by providing tax exemptions, allowances, benefits, and incentive schemes related to capital gains tax, property tax, VAT, and accelerated or free depreciation provisions. Such tax benefits have often proven to be more effective than direct subsidies in driving the adoption of energy-efficient technologies and renovations [23].

Countries such as Belgium, Denmark, the Netherlands, France, Italy, and Greece have effectively utilized tax schemes aimed at energy renovations. These measures include improvements to building envelopes, upgrades to technical systems, connections to district heating, and the installation of systems for the generation of renewable heat and electricity.

One notable approach is the tax credit system, where a percentage of the investment cost in approved technologies can be used to offset taxes. For instance, France and Italy have established robust tax credits that, although administered via income tax declarations, effectively function as direct subsidies. This mechanism can significantly lower the barrier to adoption of new

and innovative technologies by frequently updating the list of eligible measures, thus supporting the market introduction of these innovations.

5.2 Innovative financial instruments

Innovative financial instruments are newly defined financing sources tailored to address specific barriers and that have different requirements for implementation [1]. These modern approaches, including on-bill and on-tax schemes, energy performance contracting and green debt, are designed to facilitate easier access to financing for energy renovations and to align financial incentives with energy-saving outcomes.

Figure 24 - Most common innovative financing schemes [1]

5.2.1 On-bill and on-tax schemes

On-bill schemes are a financing method for energy efficiency improvements that use the energy bill as a means of repayment for investments made in energy efficiency measures. This mechanism has been in place in the US for over 30 years and has invested over \$2bn in total, of which 60% has gone to residential buildings. Despite its potential, on-bill schemes have hardly been explored in Europe [23].

On-bill schemes incorporate energy utilities into the energy renovation framework, which implies several positive features:

- Energy utilities have direct access to their customers' energy consumption, so they can target energy renovation to the worst-performing buildings without fear of private data breaches, as they already collect this information.
- The Financial Institutions may find the home renovation unattractive, as investment per home is low (compared to industrial or tertiary sectors) and the market is highly fragmented, which implies a large amount of borrowers (and therefore, higher administrative costs and default risks). However, such homes are customers of energy utilities, and the provision of energy renovation financing is linked to commercial incentives as increasing the customer loyalty or the electrification of demand (especially if the energy utility does not offer natural gas supply).
- Consumers can see how their energy-efficient behaviour translates into electricity costs, which limits the rebound effect.

On the other hand, on-tax schemes represent a new approach to financing energy renovations by integrating the repayment mechanism directly into existing tax structures. These schemes typically involve a partnership between consumers and public administrations, where the financing for energy upgrades is repaid through municipal taxes [23]. The consumer has a financial obligation with a municipality or other public administration office and the invested capital is paid periodically through municipal taxes; in most cases financing comes from the private sector and the public body acts similarly to a clearing house:

- On-tax schemes can be implemented simultaneously at national, regional, or local level, allowing for flexible criteria in line with the country's long-term building renovation strategies.

Repayment of invested capital is linked to the building tax, so if ownership is transferred, so is liability without the need for additional administrative tasks.

5.2.2 Energy performance contracting (EPC)

EPCs involve a contractual agreement in which Energy Service Companies (ESCOs) finance the upfront costs of energy performance improvement projects, with their remuneration directly tied to the energy cost savings achieved during operation. This arrangement allows property owners to upgrade their energy systems without taking on major upfront financial risks or the need to independently manage the complexities of energy efficiency projects.

Under an EPC, an ESCO not only finances and implements energy saving measures but also bears the performance risk. If the promised energy savings

are not achieved, the ESCO is contractually obliged to financially compensate the client. This setup provides a strong incentive for ESCOs to operate effectively and efficiently while giving building owners the security to invest in energy renovations without the typical risks associated with such projects.

ESCOs may use their own funds, attract third-party investment, or use a combination of both to finance energy improvements. These financing arrangements often rely on the EPC guarantee as a credit basis, making them attractive to financiers who might otherwise be reluctant to fund such projects. In countries such as Denmark, ESCO projects are typically financed by customer investments, whereas in Italy and France, large ESCOs usually finance projects themselves. In Germany and the Czech Republic, third-party financing via the EPC guarantee is common.

However, ESCO or EPC business model has serious limitations regarding energy renovation of homes:

- This model is usually implemented in the renovation of industrial buildings, where the ESCO company keeps the ownership of the asset (e.g.: in the case of replacement of the heat generator) and can decide how and when to use it. However, this is not possible for a residential renovation, which can increase the risks perceived by the ESCO company, and thus the financing costs.
- A minimum amount of energy savings is required to be able to repay the invested capital within a reasonable amortisation period. Some energy renovation measures (e.g.: modernisation of the building envelope) are known for providing energy savings over a long period of time, but the savings achieved in one year are in most cases not sufficient to cover the investment costs.

Therefore, the ESCO/EPC business model required a minimum volume of consumption and investment that in the residential context can only be achieved by renovating entire multi-family buildings, which limits the opportunities to use this scheme.

5.2.3 Green debt

Green mortgages, loans, and bonds represent an emerging class of financial instruments specifically designed to support environmental sustainability projects, including energy efficiency improvements in buildings. These financing tools are designed to incentivise investments by offering favourable terms to borrowers who meet certain “green” criteria.

- Green mortgages provide homebuyers with lower interest rates, greater borrowing capacity, or more favourable repayment terms when they purchase or renovate properties to high environmental standards. Criteria for these mortgages typically include achieving specific energy efficiency benchmarks or incorporating sustainable building practices. For example, borrowers may need to ensure their homes have a certain Energy Performance Certificate rating or incorporate renewable energy systems to qualify. The incentive structure of green mortgages encourages homeowners to invest in energy efficiency improvements by reducing their financial burden.
- Green loans are offered to individuals, businesses or projects that have environmentally sustainable goals. These could include retrofitting buildings with energy-efficient technologies, installing renewable energy systems, or undertaking projects that have a clear, measurable environmental impact. Green loans often have lower interest rates or preferential lending terms, making them an attractive option for financing energy-efficient renovations.
- Green bonds are a type of debt issued by public or private institutions which, unlike other credit instruments, are specifically intended to finance green projects.

6 Barriers

The comprehensive analysis of the renovation landscape in the target countries highlights that there are significant barriers that prevent the widespread adoption of energy-efficient renovations.

These barriers, while varying in intensity across Member States and regions, collectively contribute to the insufficient renovation rates currently observed across the EU. Addressing them is crucial for achieving the EU's energy efficiency and decarbonisation targets.

These barriers range from financial and technical challenges to regulatory and information gaps [13]. As Europe moves towards ambitious energy efficiency and sustainability targets, addressing these barriers becomes crucial to accelerate the adoption of energy-efficient practices in the building sector. This section explores the key barriers and proposes multifaceted strategies to overcome them.

6.1 Economic and financial barriers

Financial challenges [13] include not only the high upfront costs associated with implementing energy-efficient technologies but also the affordability issues that many building owners face. Access to finance is limited by traditional lending

criteria, which often fail to accommodate the unique aspects of energy renovation projects. Furthermore, the "split incentive" dilemma, where the benefits of investments are not realized by the investors (owners) but by the users (tenants), complicates the willingness to invest. There is also a perception of high opportunity costs and transaction costs, along with the presence of high discount rates which undervalue future energy savings benefits relative to immediate expenses.

6.2 Behavioural barriers

Behavioural barriers [13] come from a lack of support among consumers, fuelled by insufficient knowledge about the benefits of energy efficiency and conflicting information about actual post-renovation performance improvements. There is also widespread reluctance to the adoption of new technologies due to the perceived hassle and disruption caused by renovation processes, coupled with an aversion to debt and the financial risks associated with such projects.

6.3 Information barriers

The disparity in accessible, transparent, and comparable information [13] across EU Member States affects decisions regarding energy renovations. There is a notable lack of standardized tools that provide detailed insights into the energy performance of buildings, and potential renovators often struggle to find comprehensive details on available financial support for energy-efficient upgrades. This lack of information leads to uncertainty about the economic benefits of investing in energy efficiency.

6.4 Administrative barriers

Administrative obstacles [13] are mainly related to the complexity and length of processes involved in obtaining permits and approvals for renovation projects. Local and regional authorities often lack the technical expertise and capacity to effectively support building renovation programmes. These procedures can discourage building owners from initiating projects that are otherwise essential for energy efficiency improvements.

6.5 Technical barriers

Technical barriers [13] include a shortage of qualified professionals capable of carrying out energy renovations in an effective way. There is also a lack of standardized and industrialized solutions in the renovation market, which complicates the implementation of best practices in different projects. For non-

professional building owners, the lack of accessible consultancy services and quality assurance mechanisms makes it difficult to undertake and manage renovation projects with confidence.

6.6 Organisational barriers

Organizational challenges [13] are linked to the complexities of building ownership and management, particularly in contexts where properties are shared ownership or subject to collective decision-making. Commercial leasing arrangements further complicate this dynamic by creating split incentives between owners and tenants, which can discourage investments in energy efficiency if the benefits are not clearly aligned with the investor's interests.

7 Conclusions

The European building stock is highly inefficient, and a significant increase in investment levels will be needed to meet the targets set by the European Commission.

Investment cannot be provided by public sources alone, as there is not enough funding, and it can also have a distorting effect on the market. It has been discussed that the availability of subsidies can lead to an increase in prices, as consumers cannot bear the investment costs and therefore the price becomes irrelevant. Some market players may take advantage of this situation and inflate prices to achieve a higher mark-up. Innovative financing schemes aim to unlock the private investment needed to achieve climate neutrality by 2050 in a cost-effective way, while ensuring the competitiveness and sustainability of the EU economy. By mobilising private investment in energy renovation of buildings, but also in a broader sense - investment in energy efficiency - it will be possible to increase the cost-effectiveness of the public budget and thus increase the renovation rate and investment in all Member States.

However, for investments to be effective, it is first necessary to ensure that energy-efficient solutions providers, i.e. contractors, consultants, deployment agencies, technical offices, etc., have the necessary knowledge to implement them. Technical expertise is essential to design long-term solutions that effectively reduce energy consumption and emissions.

Energetic renovation of buildings must focus on consumers. In the case of households, people who are not always aware of the need of energy renovation, and in the case of enterprises, business owners who may not see sufficient economic benefits to pursue energy efficiency. Since barriers have a social,

technical and economic component, energy efficiency professionals need to be familiar with all aspects of energy renovation of buildings and it is not enough to specialise in one area.

8 References

- [1] European Commission (2021). 'COMMISSION STAFF WORKING DOCUMENT IMPACT ASSESSMENT REPORT Accompanying the Proposal for a Directive of the European Parliament and of the Council on the energy performance of buildings (recast)'. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/daf643a4-5da2-11ec-9c6c-01aa75ed71a1/language-en>
- [2] IDAE (Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía) (2011). 'Escala de calificación energética'. Available at: https://www.idae.es/uploads/documentos/documentos_11261_EscalaCalifEnergEdifExistentes_2011_accesible_c762988d.pdf
- [3] Ministry of Housing and Urban Agenda (2022). 'Código Técnico de la Edificación - Documento Básico Ahorro de Energía'. Available at: <https://www.codigotecnico.org/pdf/Documentos/HE/DBHE.pdf>
- [4] European Commission, EU Building Stock Observatory (2021). 'Factsheets'. Available online: <https://building-stock-observatory.energy.ec.europa.eu/factsheets/>
- [5] Eurostat (2024). 'Distribution of population by degree of urbanisation, dwelling type and income group - EU-SILC survey'. Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_lvho01/default/table?lang=en
- [6] CREA (2023). *'[Interviews with 19 market experts for a report on energy renovation of the residential building stock]'*. Unpublished
- [7] Eurostat (2024). 'Distribution of population by tenure status, type of household and income group - EU-SILC survey'. Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/ilc_lvho02/default/table?lang=en
- [8] Eurostat (2024). 'Disaggregated final energy consumption in households'. Available online: https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/databrowser/view/nrg_d_hhq/default/table?lang=en

- [9] European Commission (2022). 'Assessment of the first long-term renovation strategies under the Energy Performance of Building Directive (Art. 2a)'. Available at: [\(PDF\) Assessment of the first long-term renovation strategies under the Energy Performance of Building Directive \(Art. 2a\) \(researchgate.net\)](#)
- [10] Ministry of Transport, Mobility and Urban Agenda of the Kingdom of Spain (2020). '2020 update of the long-term strategy for energy renovation in the building sector in Spain (ERESEE)'. Available at: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-efficient-buildings/long-term-renovation-strategies_en#:~:text=The%20national%20long%2Dterm%20renovation,saving%20potential%20of%20the%20building
- [11] European Commission (2022). 'COMMISSION STAFF WORKING Analysis of the national long-term renovation strategies'. Available at: [acbdcb4c-fc23-4466-aa42-622e97ea5605_en \(europa.eu\)](acbdcb4c-fc23-4466-aa42-622e97ea5605_en)
- [12] BPIE (Buildings Performance Institute Europe) (2023). 'EU Buildings Climate Tracker: A call for faster and bolder action'. Available at: <https://www.bpie.eu/publication/eu-buildings-climate-tracker-a-call-for-faster-and-bolder-action/>
- [13] European Commission, Directorate-General for Energy (2019). 'Comprehensive study of building energy renovation activities and the uptake of nearly zero-energy building in the EU, European Commission'. Available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/97d6a4ca-5847-11ea-8b81-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-119528141>
- [14] Bertoldi, P., Economidou, M., Palermo, V., Boza-Kiss, B., Todeschi, V., (2020) How to finance energy renovation of residential buildings: Review of current and emerging financing instruments in the EU.
- [15] European Commission (2020). 'Communication from the commission to the European Parliament, The Council, The European Economic and Social Committee and The Committee of the Regions'. Available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0066>

- [16] Directive (EU) 2024/1275 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 April 2024 on the energy performance of buildings (recast). (2024) Official Journal L. Available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2024/1275/oj>
- [17] BPIE (Buildings Performance Institute Europe) (2024). The EPBD decrypted: a treasure chest of opportunities to accelerate building decarbonisation. Available at: <https://www.bpie.eu/publication/the-epbd-decrypted-a-treasure-chest-of-opportunitiesto-accelerate-building-decarbonisation/>
- [18] Della Valle, N., and Bertoldi, P., (2022) Promoting Energy Efficiency: Barriers, Societal Needs and Policies.
- [19] 'Directive (EU) 2023/1791 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 September 2023 on energy efficiency and amending Regulation (EU) 2023/955 (recast)'. (2023) Official Journal L 231, pp. 1-111. Available at: <http://data.europa.eu/eli/dir/2023/1791/oj>
- [20] European Commission, Directorate-General for energy (2023). Energy Efficiency Directive adopted, helping make the EU "Fit for 55"
- [21] European Council, Council of the European Union (2024). Fit for 55, the EU's plan for a green transition
- [22] European Commission (2024). Renovation Wave, aiming to improve energy efficiency, boost the economy and deliver better living-standards for Europeans
- [23] BEUC (The European Consumer Organisation) (2023). How to accelerate home renovations through innovative financing. Available at: <https://www.beuc.eu/news/upgrading-homes-downgrade-energy-bills-two-new-studies-making-renovation-easy>